

FUNCTIONS OF THE ALL-BUKHARA REGIONAL CONGRESS IN THE BPSR CONSTITUTION

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Annotation: On September 18-23, 1921, the II All-Bukhara Congress of people's representatives was held in Bukhara. It was attended by 648 delegates from all regions and districts. The chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic Fayzulla Khodzhayev made a report in it on the behalf of the government.

Keywords: authority, constitution, Congress, territory, right, decision

The first constitution of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic was adopted at this Congress. According to Article 15 of this basic law, it was indicated that the Congress is the Supreme state body of the Republic: “the Congress of the people's representatives of the Bukhara people's Republic or the general congress of Bukhara soviets by the second interpretation, the most superior authority of the country's office is also known as the Supreme government in the Bukhara people's Soviet Republic” [1].

Article 16 of this Constitution notes that the representatives of the regional congresses of the Central Congress of the entire Bukhara region shall have one representative per two thousand voters within the framework of each election, and the total number of Representatives at the central Congress should not exceed 350 [2]. Also, in order to discuss issues relevant to the state and come to an important decision, when adopting a one-year general program for the government office, it is established that the All-Bukhara country Congress is convened once a year.

It is specified in the basic law that the entire kurultai of Bukhara includes:

1. To approve and amend the Basic Laws of the Bukhara People's Republic;
2. To guide the entire domestic and foreign policy of the Bukhara People's Republic;

3. To determine the borders (frontiers) of the country, to change them and to renounce some part of the territories and rights of the country or some rights;
4. To set the borders of the country, to change them and to give up some part of the country or any rights;
5. To designate the borders of the regions in the disposal of country;
6. To know the criteria and weighing methods in the country and to change them;
7. Issuance of money;
8. Establish relations with foreign countries;
9. To declare war and conclude a peace treaty;
10. To approve peace treaties;
11. Take domestic and foreign loans, create commercial and customs offices and engage in finance with similar relationships;
11. To draw up a common economic action “plan” for the state;
12. To determine the place (domestic and foreign) of the Republic of Bukhara People's Councils;
16. To enact laws defining the ways of entering and leaving Bukhara citizenship (citizenship) and the rights of foreign subjects living on the territory of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic;
17. To announce general and private amnesty [3].

During the negotiations on March 30, 1920 in Bukhara, conducted by the official Soviet delegation headed by Mikhail Frunze, the emir was presented with an ultimatum, according to which he had to put Soviet money into circulation on the territory of the state, facilitate the deployment of Red Army troops on the territory of Bukhara and maintain the Kagan-Termez railway in working condition through the territory of the emirate that cuts the communications of Russia. After the emir refused to comply with the demands, a military operation was prepared and a

“revolution” was carried out, which consisted in the occupation of Bukhara by the Red Army on September 2.

The Main Law, adopted at the II Congress of All-Bukhara People's Representatives, differs from the 1918 Constitution of the Russian Federation in a number of important issues. Article 6 of it states that “the right to dispose of and use the acquired or inherited private property as desired.”

Also, the article on the violence of the poor (dictatorship of the proletariat) appointed by Article 9 of the Basic Law of Russia was not included in the constitution of the USSR, because Bukhara was not a socialist state under the rule of the dictatorship of the proletariat, but a people's republic established on the basis of democracy (Later, after Fitrat and other political figures were removed from office the constitution was amended and a special article on the violence of the poor (dictatorship of the proletariat) was forcibly introduced) [4].

In conclusion, after the formation of the Bukhara People's Soviet republic, the All-Bukhara Country Congress was declared the supreme body that would govern the country. The role and authority of this Congress in the adoption of important decisions on the management of the Republic has become great. However, the Bolsheviks hindered the Independent administration of the young republic by local personnel. The result was the unreasonable interference of the Bukhara Communist Party, formed by the Bolsheviks, in the activities of the All-Bukhara country Congress, which was convened four times.

REFERENCES:

1. National Archives of Uzbekistan, fund 47, list 1, volume 13,11-p.
2. National Archives of Uzbekistan, fund 47, list 1, volume 13, 11-p.
3. National Archives of Uzbekistan, fund 47, list 1, volume 13, 10-11-pp.
4. Boltaboev H. The role of Abdurauf Fitrat in the statehood of the Bukhara People's Republic / Articles of the International Symposium dedicated to the 100th Anniversary of the Republic of Bukhara People's Soviets.– İstanbul: Kutlu Yayınevi va (Taşkent: “Mumtoz”). 2021. –p.118.

5. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.
6. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 197-202.
7. Sobirovich T. B. Issues of gender equality in uzbekistan: Strategy of reforms //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 203-207.
8. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 131-135.
9. Sobirovich T. B. Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development //Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IIJSR). – 2021.
10. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 229-233.
11. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 122-126.
12. Sobirovich T. B., Murodogli I. S. The strategy for the implementation of the modern governance system in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 741-748.
13. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of spiritual renewal in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – T. 24. – №. 06.
14. Sobirovich T. B. The criterion of human indicators in development and renewals in Uzbekistan //EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR). – 2020. – T. 6. – №. 8. – C. 509-511.

15. Sobirovich T. B. Oʻzbekiston demokratik jamiyat taraqqiyoti rivojida maʼnaviy yangilanishlar strategiyasining roli //Imom Buxoriy saboqlari. – 2020. – №. 2. – C. 118-121.